

Design and GVT of a dynamically scaled wing structure for fuel sloshing investigations

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The effect of fuel sloshing on aircraft wings is currently being investigated in the Airbus-led Sloshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD) project with the aim of passively alleviating the gust loads on commercial aircraft. This work represents a step up in the experimental investigations of sloshing-induced damping in aircraft wings. A reduced-scale wing model is presented with a design based on genetic algorithm optimization for static and dynamic scaling. A good level of matching is shown with the scaled displacement field, target frequencies and mode shapes. Additional challenges when including the scaled fuel tank are discussed. Ground vibration tests (GVT) are conducted on the manufactured scaled structure to assess its dynamic properties and provide data for finite element model updating and further numerical and experimental sloshing investigations.

I. Nomenclature

a_n	=	parameterization coefficients
A	=	parameterization function
b	=	wing span
f^s	=	scaled structure modal frequency
f^T	=	target modal frequency
F_S	=	static scaling objective function
F_{M1}, F_{M2}	=	dynamic scaling objective functions
$F^{(y)}$	=	in plane vibration modes
$F^{(z)}$	=	out of plane vibration modes
H, R, W	=	cross-sectional dimensions
i, j	=	indices
\mathbf{k}_c	=	connection stiffness parameter vector
\mathbf{k}_r	=	root stiffness parameter vector
LC	=	set of load cases
MC	=	set of mode shapes
y_s	=	normalized span-wise coordinate
α	=	accelerance
δ^s	=	scaled structure displacement
δ^T	=	target displacement
Δf	=	frequency error
ζ	=	damping ratio
λ_a	=	acceleration scale
λ_f	=	frequency scale
λ_F	=	force scale
λ_L	=	length scale
λ_ρ	=	density scale
ϕ^s	=	scaled structure mode shape
ϕ^T	=	target mode shape

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II. Introduction and Background

LIQUID sloshing inside wing-tanks is currently being studied as a means of passively reducing the gust response of aircraft structures. Sloshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD) is an EU-funded, Airbus-led project that has the aim of studying the feasibility of exploiting the dynamic interaction between airliner wing structures and the fuel carried inside of them in order to reduce the response to gusts and turbulence. The goal is to obtain less conservative designs by reducing the wing root loads as a consequence of taking into account the additional fuel sloshing-induced damping.

As part of the SLOWD project, multiple investigations have been carried out to assess the behaviour of liquids inside containers, under excitation conditions similar to what would be encountered in the case of an aircraft. Constantin *et al.* [1] presented a novel vertical excitation rig that allowed for high amplitude, low structural damping experiments and isolation of liquid sloshing damping effects following step release excitation. The authors demonstrated the expected damping behaviour when only the vertical component of the wing bending motion is isolated and showed that sloshing-induced damping was substantial in such a system, was maximized at 0.5 filling fraction and exhibited substantially different characteristics depending on amplitude of excitation. This work was continued for mid-range amplitudes of excitation in [2]. Martinez-Carasscal *et al.* [3] showed similar results in a springs-based rig under vertical excitation. Damping due to vertical sloshing was recently shown in a beam experiment by Titurus *et al.* [4], where the authors showed highly nonlinear sloshing-induced damping. Constantin *et al.* [5] and De Courcy *et al.* [6] presented a sloshing surface identification methodology and applied it to numerical model comparison and calibration. Such experimental work is used, beside providing an understanding of the fundamental physical interactions, to create equivalent mechanical models (EMM) and reduced order models (ROM) with predictive capabilities. For vertical sloshing, such models involve bouncing balls interacting with vertically oscillating tanks, such as the models presented in [1, 7]. De Courcy *et al.* [8] proposed a bouncing-ball model coupled with an aeroelastic wing model that showed dissipative effects at multiple gust lengths. The effect of vertical sloshing is also being taken into account via ROMs trained on and tested against CFD data, as in [9, 10]. High-fidelity models are also considered as part of the SLOWD project, either based on Volume of Fluid (e.g. [11]) or Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics ([12, 13]). The present paper is a continuation of experimental sloshing-induced damping investigations applied to a more complex, wing-like structure.

Experimental investigations in any engineering field involves testing of models. Testing on full-scale structures is not always possible or desirable, cost considerations being an important factor. Scaled structures are thus studied, based upon scaling rules stemming from the fundamental principles that govern the physics of the problem [14]. Particular to this work, a scaled structure based on a research wing prototype was designed and built for the study of sloshing-induced damping as well as to mitigate the risks associated with full-scale sloshing tests. For the particular application in this work, the reduced-scale wing must exhibit the same static and dynamic behaviour, a problem which is similar to the more general one of aeroelastic scaling. Model scaling is problem-specific and, for instance, a scaled wing will look completely different when scaled for aerodynamic similarity as compared to structural dynamics similarity. Bisplinghoff *et al.* [15] established the principles that have to be followed for aeroelastic scaling: the scaled structure must have the same distribution of structural stiffness, the same external shape presented to the airstream and the same mass distribution. Based on these principles, multiple approaches have been historically taken towards aeroelastic scaling.

French [16] presented an optimization-based method for the stiffness design of aeroelastic models. French and Eastep [17] extended this procedure to cover mass design as well, allowing for complete structural scaling of wind-tunnel aeroelastic models. The process described in [17] involves two separate steps: stiffness design by matching static displacements between the full-scale and scaled structure and then a mass design using lumped masses to match natural frequencies and mode shapes. A similar procedure was used by Pereira *et al.* [18] for the aeroelastic scaling of a joined-wing aircraft. Overall, 10 vibration modes were matched to within 8% error and the results were found to be in good agreement with the ground vibration tests. Blair *et al.* [19] and Miller *et al.* [20] presented similar optimization processes for the aeroelastic scaling of high-altitude, long-endurance joined-wing aircraft and showed good results. An approach based on a single spar with cruciform cross-section was described by Yusuf *et al.* [21], where the stiffness distribution was controlled by continuously varying the cross-sectional dimensions of the spar. All of these two-step-optimization based approaches are particularly appealing due to their modularity and demonstrated applicability in practice.

There have been proposed ways to include geometrical nonlinearity in the aeroelastic design process. Due to computational costs, the problem of aeroelastic scaling when nonlinear geometrical effects are taken into account is non-trivial. Wan and Cesnik [22] presented a nonlinear aeroelastic scaling approach based on a decomposition of the stiffness matrix and concluded that the aeroelastic scaling laws for linear structures are suitable for geometrically

nonlinear structures undergoing large deformations as well. Bond *et al.* [23] demonstrated that by matching the buckling eigenvalue, the geometrically nonlinear response of the system will also yield similar results up to 60% of the critical buckling load. But perhaps the most elegant approach taken to tackle geometrical nonlinearities in aeroelastic scaling is represented by the Equivalent Static Loads (ESL) method. Introduced initially to handle dynamic loads in optimization problems by Kang *et al.* [24], ESL has been adapted by Park [25] to nonlinear problems as well. An equivalent set of linear loads is used, that generates the same displacement field as an analysis which is not linear [26]. Ricciardi *et al.* [27] demonstrated the use of the ESL method for the nonlinear aeroelastic scaling of a 1:9 scale model. Spada *et al.* [28] presented a similar optimization approach for aeroelastic scaling based on ESL; the difference from Ricciardi *et al.* [27] was the usage of a two-step optimization process, optimizing first for stiffness and then for mass, similarly to [17]. A similar scaling approach to what is found in the aeroelastic scaling literature is employed in the current work, with the notable difference that in our case we are not interested in the *aerodynamic* part of the problem. Instead, the static and dynamic behaviour of the full-scale and scaled structures are matched.

In this current work we present the outline of a wing model that was scaled for sloshing-induced energy dissipation similarity. The design of the scaled model is presented and discussed in relation to the full-scale wing-box. A two-step genetic algorithm is presented for the static and dynamic scaling problems, with the particularities of the problem at hand. A series of results pertaining to the level of matching between the scaled and full-scale wing are presented and discussed. Based on the design presented here, an experimental rig was partially manufactured and ground vibration tests have been conducted. The experimental modal analysis data was used to update the finite element model by including joints and root cantilever details that were not captured in the initial design; this in turn allows for calibrated numerical investigations in the future. This work is an important starting point for future wing fuel-sloshing tests.

III. Scaled wing model geometry

It is not feasible to directly scale down the structure to be modelled. As presented in Section II, quantities that are of interest for the specific sloshing problem must be isolated and scaled accordingly. Multiple scaled wing model configurations have been proposed in order to scale the structural response of the wing. Classically, Bisplinghoff [15] discussed spars with cruciform cross-sections (also used in [21]), two-spar torque-tube models, welded-steel torque-box or plate-like configurations. Each of these configurations have benefits depending on aspect ratio and specific application. In this work we used a two-spars torque-tube model, as shown in Figure 1 together with the full-scale wingbox for comparison. This geometrical configuration was chosen for two main reasons: (1) ease of parameter definition for the design problem and (2) the need to fit a scaled fuel tank on top of the structure. The two spars' cross sectional dimensions are rectangular and varying in 10 steps. Overall, 5 torque tubes are used with circular cross-section. The chosen geometrical configuration thus enables the variation of 45 cross-sectional dimensions, allowing for the stiffness distribution of the scaled structure to be matched with the full-scale one.

A Buckingham Pi analysis [14] was conducted as a preliminary step, similar to the analysis presented in [3]. The sloshing-induced dissipative energy was found to be dependent on multiple non-dimensional quantities, the most important of which are presented in Table 1.

Length scale λ_L	0.2
Frequency scale λ_f	2.24
Force scale λ_F	0.008
Acceleration scale λ_a	1
Density scale λ_ρ	1

Table 1 Scaling constants used for scaled model design

Each scaling constant is defined as the ratio of the scaled to full-scale quantity. From a geometrical point of view, the model is thus five times smaller than the full-scale wing. The span, root and tip chords were scaled and the sweep and dihedral angles were preserved. The fuel tank was directly geometrically scaled according to the λ_L length scale. As full-scale experiments are planned for the future, liquids with the same density ($\lambda_\rho = 1$) will be used for both full-scale and scaled experiments.

Fig. 1 Full-scale wingbox (upper side) and scaled structure (lower side)

IV. Static and dynamic scaling via GA optimization

The approach taken in this work is based on a two-level optimization process designed to match both the static deflections and the first three modal shapes and frequencies (first two out-plane and first in-plane bending modes), between the scaled structure and target full-scale wing structural model. A genetic algorithm (GA) was used to minimize the cost function by applying genetic operators on successive generations, thereby imitating the processes found in nature and incrementally arriving at better solutions in consecutive generations. In-depth presentation of GAs, their properties and operators are beyond the scope of this paper, but comprehensive explanations can be found in references such as [29]. The structure of the GA follows the genetic operators discussed by Holst and Pulliam in [30] and uses real-value encoding for the variables. An overview of the algorithm applied to the problem presented here is given in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Two-step optimization loop for static and dynamic scaling

A first level of optimization (left-hand side in Figure 2) is represented by the static scaling and is comprised of the

following main steps: (1) a set of initial structures are pseudo-randomly generated, (2) the scaled static deformations are evaluated and compared to the target deformation field, (3) if the obtained deformations do not satisfactorily match the target values, (4) apply genetic operators to modify the spars and torque tubes and (5) go to the next step and re-evaluate the structures. Since there is no mathematical assurance that a global minimum of the optimization function is ever reached for such a problem, convergence in the sense of step number (3) described above is evaluated depending on the convergence history (see for example Figure 5).

After the static scaling is completed and the displacement field is scaled, the second level of optimization (right-hand side in Figure 2) is started: (1) lumped masses distributed over the statically scaled structure are pseudo-randomly initialized; (2) the first three natural modes of vibration are evaluated and then (3) the mode shapes and frequencies are compared to the target ones; (4) if the level of matching is not adequate, the distributed masses are modified and (5) the algorithm advances to the next step and re-evaluates the natural modes.

The algorithm was implemented using the Matlab R2019a environment and the objective functions were evaluated using FE models implemented in Nastran 2018.1 (SOL 101 for static scaling and SOL 103 for dynamic scaling). The static and dynamic scaling procedures each have their particularities which will be discussed separately in the following sections.

A. Static scaling

The idea of the static scaling is simple: loads that are scaled using the force scale λ_F given in Table 1 must cause static deflections that are scaled by the λ_L factor. However, there is no single force that can be applied to the structures such that torsional and in and out of plane bending deflections can be evaluated. Consequently, the three load cases presented in Figure 3 are considered: LC1 and LC2 – vertical forces applied at the tip of the structures, at leading and trailing edge, and LC3 – horizontal force applied at the tip of the structures. Together, the three load cases ensure that the static bending and torsional responses are matched. For an applied force F on the scaled structure, a force $\lambda_F^{-1} F$ is applied on the full-scale structure; displacements δ obtained for the scaled structure are compared to displacements $\lambda_L^{-1} \delta$ obtained for the full-scale structure.

Fig. 3 Load cases used for static scaling

In order to keep the problem manageably small, several dimensional reductions are made. A subset of 20 points is used as stations for displacement comparison and only the dominant displacement components for each load case is used: z displacements for LC1 and 2, and y displacements for LC3. The 20 control points are shown in Figure 4 where a displacement δ_j^i for point no. j and load case no. i is exemplified.

Fig. 4 Control points used for static and dynamic scaling

The objective function for the static scaling is

$$F_S = \sum_{i \in \text{LC}} \left[w_i \sum_{j \in S} \left(\frac{\delta_j^{is} - \delta_j^{iT}}{\max(\delta^{iT})} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

where LC is the set of load cases considered, w_i are weights given to each load case, S is the set of reference points used for displacement matching, δ_j^{is} is the displacement of the scaled structure at reference point j for load case i , δ_j^{iT} is the target displacement at the same point and δ^{iT} is the target displacement vector for load case i . The in-plane behaviour of the structure is of secondary importance for vertical sloshing studies, therefore the weights considered for each load case are $\mathbf{w} = \langle 2, 2, 1 \rangle$. The third load case is the one considering in-plane loading, such that more weight is given to the out-plane response of the structure during the static optimization.

The parameters that are modified by the GA in order to minimize the objective function in Equation 1 are: the widths (W) and heights (H) of the rectangular cross-section spars and the radii (R) of the torque tubes. The spars' cross-sections are varying in 10 steps and there are 5 torque tubes, resulting in a total of 45 parameters. In order to reduce the number of optimization parameters, thus reducing the dimension of the problem, the following polynomial parameterization is employed

$$A(x_s) = \sum_{n=0}^3 a_n x_s^n \quad (2)$$

where $x_s \in [0, 1]$ is the normalized span-wise coordinate (evaluated at the discrete span-wise positions of the 20 control points), A is the parameter being varied (W , H and R respectively), and a_n are the parameterization coefficients. The parameterization presented in Equation 2 reduces the number of optimization parameters to 20 (four parameters a for each spar and torque tube cross-sectional dimension).

Multiple constraints are imposed on the optimization parameters in order to limit the search space and to eliminate undesired designs:

$$a_{n1} \leq a_n \leq a_{n2} \quad (3a)$$

$$\frac{dA}{dx_s} \leq 0 \quad (3b)$$

$$A(1) > A_{min} \quad (3c)$$

In Equation 3a, a_{n1} and a_{n2} are lower and upper bounds applied to the coefficients a_n from Equation 2 in order to set limits to the spar root cross-sectional dimensions and variation rates across the span. Equation 3b ensures that the dimensions decrease along the span, and Equation 3c imposes a minimum value on the tip cross-sectional dimensions for practical reasons. Together, the constraints ensure that the GA search is limited to a feasible domain.

B. Dynamic scaling

Once the static response of the scaled structure is matched to the target, the second step involving the mass optimization is divided into two parts: (1) modal frequency optimization, and (2) mode shape optimization. Three mode shapes and frequencies were considered for the mass optimization namely, in the order of the increasing modal frequency: first out-plane bending mode, first in-plane bending mode and second out-plane bending mode. For the study of the sloshing-induced damping, matching these three modes and frequencies was considered sufficient, with the out-plane bending modes usually dominating the gust response of wing structures and thus driving the liquid response inside the tank. The target error for the frequency optimization is set at 5% and the objective function is

$$F_{M1} = \sum_{k \in \text{MC}} \left(\frac{f_k^s - f_k^T}{f_k^T} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where MC is the set of considered mode shapes, f_k^s is the scaled structure modal frequency of mode k , f_k^T is the target modal frequency of mode k . The parameters being varied are lumped masses positioned at the control points presented in Figure 4.

The second step in dynamic scaling starts when at least 10% of the structures in a generation have the first three modal frequencies within 5% error of the target. During the second step, optimization is done for the mode shape

matching and a penalty is applied to the structures that have a modal frequency error higher than 5%. The mode shapes are normalized to the maximum value and the following correction is applied in order to ensure mode shape sign consistency between the scaled and full-scale models [31]:

$$\phi_k^s = \frac{\phi_k^{s0} \cdot \phi_k^T}{\|\phi_k^{s0}\| \cdot \|\phi_k^T\|} \cdot \phi_k^{s0} \quad (5)$$

where ϕ_k^s is the sign-consistent scaled structure mode shape for mode k , ϕ_k^{s0} is the initial scaled structure mode shape for mode k and ϕ_k^T is the target mode shape for mode k .

The first three normal mode shapes are matched to the full-scale model. The objective function is formulated as a normalized difference between the current and target mode shapes:

$$F_{M2} = \sum_{k \in MC} \sum_{i \in S} \left(\frac{\phi_k^{iT} - \phi_k^{is}}{\max \phi_k^T} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

where MC is the set of considered mode shapes, S is the set of control points, ϕ_k^{iT} is the i^{th} control point displacement for target mode shape k and ϕ_k^{is} is i^{th} control point displacement for the scaled structure mode shape k . The control points used for the mode shape comparison are the same as those used for static scaling, presented in Figure 4.

The only constraint applied on the lumped masses was that the mass of one lumped element should not exceed 2kg.

C. Results

Selected optimization results are presented in this section. An example of the convergence history for the stiffness optimization is presented in Figure 5. Such a history of the fitness function value was used to judge the convergence properties of the algorithm and to ensure that the cost function reached its minimum in the established search space. A number of 500 generations, each with 20 structures (chromosomes, in the context of GA) was generally sufficient to obtain satisfactory results.

Fig. 5 Convergence history example for the stiffness optimization

One important requirement imposed by the current investigation was that the liquid flow inside the fuel tank should be observable from the outside, such that the sloshing motion analysis can be conducted on a visual basis. The sloshing observability requirements made fuel tank integration with the scaled wing structure restrictive and lead to the solution presented in Figure 1, with the tank fitted on top of the structure. From the scaling and optimization point of view, this aspect raised multiple challenges, such that the selected optimization results will be discussed separately for a structure with and without fuel tank attached.

1. Scaled structure without fuel tank

The optimization algorithm was first applied to the structure without the fuel tank attached to it. The main difference between the case where the tank is attached and not is that the tank introduces substantial additional stiffness and mass to the system; it has a size comparable to the wing structure itself, as can be seen in Figure 1.

The main results for the static scaling stage can be presented in the form of the match obtained between the two displacement fields. Figure 6 shows the static displacements of the statically scaled structure when compared to the target for all load cases considered, normalized to the maximum displacement value. For brevity, only the leading edge control point values are shown; the structure is torsionally stiff and there is no visual difference between the LE and TE displacements.

Fig. 6 Normalized control point deflections across the wing span compared to the target values

The satisfactory solution was found for the stepped spars and torque tubes cross-sectional dimensions that scaled the displacement field correctly for the considered out-plane, in-plane and torsional static response. The displacement error at each control point is within the 5% target of the optimization algorithm.

The dynamic scaling results obtained after optimizing the mass distribution across the statically scaled structure are presented in Figure 7. The three mode shapes are seen to correspond well to the target ones and the frequency error is within the 5% bound.

Fig. 7 Mode shape comparison to the target shapes at the control points

The mode shape matching can be quantified using the Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC). The MAC [32] measures the degree of similarity or collinearity between two modal vectors and takes the values between 0 (no correlation) and 1 (perfect correlation). Generally, a MAC value above 0.9 indicates good similarity between the two modal vectors [33]. Mode shape 1 (first out-plane bending mode) shows virtually perfect match with the target, with a MAC value of 1; the other two modes both show MAC values above 0.98, so a very good level of matching was obtained between all considered modes.

2. Scaled structure with the fuel tank

There are certain challenges when the fuel tank is included in the design process, as described in the beginning of Section IV.C. Figure 8 shows the three static load case deflections when the tank was included in the optimization process. There is a good level of matching between the scaled and full-scale structures for the first two load cases, while reduced agreement is seen for the in-plane bending load case. The tank-structure connection is designed to uncouple the tank to a certain degree from the primary structure by allowing it to slide axially relative to the scaled wing. The same strategy was considered for the in-plane bending and, as can be seen in Figure 8c, this causes substantial local stiffening effects.

Fig. 8 Normalized control point deflections across the wing span compared to the target values

For the dynamic scaling to be successfully conducted and lumped masses to be used, the scaled-structure’s modal frequencies after the first optimization level must be higher than the target frequencies. After the tank was included in the design, the natural frequencies after the static scaling were lower than the target ones as a consequence of the significant added tank mass. Figure 9 shows the normal mode shape and frequency matching results.

Fig. 9 Mode shape comparison to the target values at the control points

The MAC value for mode shape number 1 is 0.98 and the frequency is 3% lower than the targeted one. The other two modes do not show as good an agreement; there is a notable local stiffening effect produced by the fuel tank, which can best be seen in Figures 9b and 9c. Notably, in the case of mode shape 3, the MAC value seems to overestimate the degree of modal discrepancy. For the liquid sloshing investigation purposes, the most important vibration mode to be scaled correctly is the first out-plane bending mode, as that mode dominates the response of the wing under gust excitation.

V. Evaluation of modal behaviour of scaled structure and model updating

The resulting manufactured structure is presented in Figure 10 in the cantilevered configuration and set at 0 deg dihedral angle. The materials used are Aluminium of type Formodal 036 T6 (with the properties as indicated by the manufacturer: density $\rho = 2779 \text{ kg/m}^3$, Young’s modulus $E = 72 \text{ GPa}$ and Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.33$) for the spars and torque tubes and mild steel for the root connections. The torque tubes and spars are joined together via bolted connections; the wall interface design is based on the brackets that provide high stiffness in the vertical direction, the main loading direction of interest for the vertical sloshing studies. Two interface steel plates allow for a rigid connection to the reaction wall as well as relatively easy access to interchange with the second set of angled wedges at the root. Figure 10b shows the instrumentation positioning across the structure: 10 accelerometers are used in the z (vertical) direction, among which one is at the root for background noise monitoring (accelerometer 0) and one is at the driving point (accelerometer D). Four accelerometers positioned across the leading edge spar measure accelerations in the y (horizontal, in-plane) direction. A force sensor (sensor L) is placed between an electromagnetic shaker’s stinger and the structure at the point D,L indicated in Figure 10b. Identical uniaxial accelerometers (PCB 333M07) and a force transducer (PCB 208C03) are used to measure the output from the system, and an LDS electrodynamic shaker was used to provide the excitation signal. The instrumentation allows for complete acquisition of the data required for

experimental modal analysis of the presented structure. Results based on the spar-torque tube structure are going to be presented and discussed, since manufacturing delays prevented the analysis of the structure with the fuel tank attached.

Fig. 10 Experimental setup – structure cantilevered to the reaction wall and instrumentation

A. Experimental modal analysis in cantilevered configuration

The focus of the experimental modal analysis (EMA) testing is to provide the modal parameters of the structure with two aims in mind: (1) to obtain a thorough understanding of the dry dynamics of the primary structure before proceeding with the liquid tank installation and (2) to obtain experimental data for the calibration and updating of the finite element beam model. For the out of plane vibration modes (z axis direction), the data were collected and processed using Simcentre TestLab 18 software package and its MIMO module. The processing of the data was done using the PolyMAX algorithm [34] in the same software package. The in-plane vibration modes were analysed using

impact testing with the modal hammer, as a larger number of accelerometers would have been needed to instrument the structure appropriately in the in-plane direction. The in-plane behaviour of this structure is not the focus of this work, since the liquid sloshing motion of interest primarily interacts with the vertical motion.

The excitation used was burst a random input with a duration of 64s. Considering the very light damping levels observed experimentally, out of the 64s of the acquisition time, the burst stage was limited to 10% (6.4s) of the overall test run duration. The shaker excitation was applied in the vertical direction and 6 consecutive runs were used to generate the averaged responses. Additional impact hammer tests were conducted separately in order to characterise the in-plane behaviour of the structure.

Figure 11 shows the stabilization diagram for the burst random excitation tests. The stabilization diagram is a convenient way of graphically indicating the natural frequencies of the structure and represents the key step in the modal parameter identification. A system order of up to 32 was used for the analysis and a series of well-separated vibration modes are identified across the frequency range of interest, with "s" symbols indicating the mode identification stability in both frequency and damping values.

Fig. 11 Stabilization diagram for modal parameter identification

The modal properties are summarised in Table 2, with the modes numbered by increasing frequency and categorized by the dominant mode shape direction. The frequency range of interest covers three out-plane bending modes and two torsional modes. The differences in experimentally identified modal frequencies and the numerical predictions (Δf) range between 1.8% and 10%, generally increasing with the mode number. The experimental values are lower than the numerically predicted ones. This is indicative of the differences in the realised structural stiffness and mass distribution due to manufacturing and boundary condition imperfections. The differences are higher in the in-plane direction, mainly due to the boundary conditions which are not optimal for the in-plane stiffness (see the vertically oriented root brackets in Figure 10a). The structure is very lightly damped, as can be seen in the corresponding column in Table 2: the first bending mode of the structure has a modal damping ratio $\zeta = 0.02\%$. Despite these differences in the predicted modal frequencies, there is a very good agreement between the experimental and numerical mode shapes, with the MAC values ranging between 0.99 and 1, showing excellent match across all vibration modes. Figure 12 provides a visual indication of the mode shapes, both experimental and numerical, using the coordinates of the accelerometers shown in Figure 10b to discretize the shapes along the leading and trailing edge spars.

Based on these experimental data, the initial finite element model was updated to improve its predictive capability.

(a) Mode $F_1^{(z)}$

(b) Mode $F_4^{(z)}$

(c) Mode $F_5^{(z)}$

(d) Mode $F_7^{(z)}$

(e) Mode $F_9^{(z)}$

Fig. 12 Experimental and numerical model comparison between mode shapes. Red – trailing edge (TE) points, Blue – Leading edge (LE) points; solid lines – experimental data, dashed lines – numerical data

Out of plane modes (z)				
Mode #	Δf [%]	ζ [%]	MAC	Description
1	-1.8	0.02	1.00	1 st bending
4	-2.5	0.03	1.00	2 nd bending
5	-5.7	0.13	1.00	1 st torsional
7	-3.7	0.26	1.00	3 rd bending
9	-10.0	0.29	0.99	2 nd torsional
In plane modes (y)				
2	-18.4	0.13	0.99	1 st bending
3	-16.1	0.16	0.99	2 nd bending
6	-8.3	0.11	0.99	3 rd bending
8	-2.3	0.13	0.99	4 th bending

Table 2 Identified modal properties compared to the uncalibrated numerical model

Root					
$k_{\theta y}^r$ [Nm/rad]	$k_{\theta z}^r$ [Nm/rad]	k_y^r [N/m]			
$3 \cdot 10^6$	$2.5 \cdot 10^5$	$3 \cdot 10^5$			
Joints					
k_x [N/m]	k_y [N/m]	k_z [N/m]	$k_{\theta x}$ [Nm/rad]	$k_{\theta y}$ [Nm/rad]	$k_{\theta z}$ [Nm/rad]
$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$

Table 3 Baseline parameters for model updating

B. Vibration mode sensitivity analysis and finite element model updating

In order to improve the agreement between the numerically predicted and experimental modal frequencies, the fidelity of the numerical model is increased through addition of a number of the lumped stiffness and mass elements that account for the physical details that were not modelled before the manufacturing stage was completed. Figure 13 shows a schematic of the structure used for model updating. The beam model used for the initial design, as presented in Section IV, worked under a series of simplifying assumptions which we now eliminate:

- The cantilever condition was imposed in a mathematically perfect way by adding the nodal degree of freedom displacement constraints in all 6 directions at the root. Such hard constraints are partly replaced with a series of linear and torsional springs that account for flexibility at the root. An array $\mathbf{k}_r = \langle k_{\theta y}^r, k_{\theta z}^r, k_y^r \rangle$ describes the root stiffness in the y (in-plane) direction and around the y and z axis (rotational degrees of freedom). The $k_{\theta y}^r$ stiffness accounts for the rigidity at the root in the out-plane direction, while $k_{\theta z}^r$ and k_y^r are used for the in-plane direction.
- The joints between the torque tubes and spars were represented as nodal coincidence conditions in the original FE model and are now replaced with the global array $\mathbf{k}_c = \langle k_x, k_y, k_z, k_{\theta x}, k_{\theta y}, k_{\theta z} \rangle$, accompanied by the bolt masses m_b (5 to 40 gr depending on the spanwise position). This joint parameterisation is applied globally, where the same parameter values are used across all torque tube to spar connections.
- The masses of accelerometers are included as $m_a = 15$ gr each and they take into account a lumped approximation of the additional wire masses as well; this was found to be important for the matching at the two highest frequencies considered.

A sensitivity analysis is carried out based on the 9 stiffness parameters in order to identify the influence on each vibration mode. The baseline parameter values are presented in Table 3 and were chosen to provide a satisfactory preliminary level of matching. Each parameter was then perturbed by 5% of its nominal value and the changes in each modal frequency were recorded. The results are presented in the matrix in Figure 14, where each entry (i, j) represents the percentage change in the modal frequency i as a consequence of the independent variation in parameter j . The entries are colour-coded such that the darker values in each row indicate higher frequency variations.

Fig. 13 Parameters used for model tuning

Root					
k'_{θ_y} [Nm/rad]	k'_{θ_z} [Nm/rad]	k'_y [N/m]			
$2.45 \cdot 10^6$	$5.9 \cdot 10^4$	$2.5 \cdot 10^6$			
Joints					
k_x [N/m]	k_y [N/m]	k_z [N/m]	k_{θ_x} [Nm/rad]	k_{θ_y} [Nm/rad]	k_{θ_z} [Nm/rad]
$8.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$	$7.5 \cdot 10^6$

Table 4 Tuned parameters for the updated FE model

The root variable k'_{θ_y} has an influence only on the out-plane modes, as it controls the root stiffness in the rotational direction around the y axis. Similarly, only the in-plane modes are sensitive to variations in k'_{θ_z} and k'_y . These results correspond with the intended purpose of these parameters and serves as an initial check of the results obtained. The FE model was tuned starting with the parameters that have the most influence on the first two bending modes, namely the root stiffness values. Figure 14 shows that the higher out-plane modes frequencies ($F_5^{(z)}$, $F_7^{(z)}$ and $F_9^{(z)}$) are most sensitive to k_{θ_y} , which was consequently used to improve the agreement in the higher frequency out-plane bending modes. In fact, a suitable combination of parameters was not found such that all three modes 5, 7 and 9 are correctly tuned at the same time; in order to increase the agreement, the accelerometers masses were added, which then brought the k_{θ_y} back to its baseline value and provided the final results for all of the out-plane bending modes. In terms of in-plane modal tuning, apart from the root parameters, k_x was used to additionally fine-tune the first two bending modes, the higher frequency in-plane dynamics being considered a low priority in this work.

Out of plane modes (updated model)		
Mode #	Δf [%]	MAC
1	0.0	1.00
4	0.1	1.00
5	0.0	1.00
7	-0.3	1.00
9	0.0	0.99
In plane modes (updated model)		
2	0.0	0.98
3	0.5	0.96

Table 5 Comparison between the updated numerical modal frequencies and experimental results

The obtained level of agreement following FE model updating is presented in Table 5. All of the first three out-plane vibration modes were tuned to the differences in their frequency of less than 0.1%. The mode shapes were not substantially altered and the MAC values between the experimental and numerical model indicate a very good match.

A final indication of the pre and post updated dynamic behaviour of the FE model can be obtained by evaluating

Fig. 14 Sensitivity analysis for model updating

(a) Driving point acceleration ($\alpha_{D,D}$)

(b) Tip trailing edge acceleration ($\alpha_{D,1z}$)

Fig. 15 Frequency response functions (z) match between experimental data, raw FE model and updated FE model

the frequency response functions in comparison to the experimental data. Nastran SOL 111 was used to execute the numerical frequency response studies. The input force was localized at the same point as in the experimental setup (point D in Figure 10b) and had a value of 1N across the frequency range of interest. The modal damping values measured experimentally were included as well (Table 2). Figure 15 shows the driving point acceleration ($\alpha_{D,D}$) for the experimental case, as well as the numerical predictions for the raw and tuned FE models. For comparison purposes, due to the low signal to noise ratio in the acceleration measured at the driving point at low frequencies, the tip trailing edge acceleration ($\alpha_{D,1z}$) is included as well in Figure 15b. The driving point frequency response function shows a stiffness-dominated characteristic [33], as it drifts upwards at higher frequencies, with antiresonances occurring immediately after resonances, as expected. At low frequencies there is an inertia-dominated upwards trend, indicative of perhaps small movements at the root of the structure due to imperfect mechanical contacts and constraint. This aspect will be investigated further in the future.

The predictive capability of the model before updating is seen to be adequate for the first two modal frequencies, which is to be expected considering that the first two out-plane bending modes were also used for the dynamic scaling, as discussed in Section IV.B. However, the level of matching across the entire frequency of interest is greatly improved by the applied model updating procedure.

VI. Conclusions

A scaled wing model was designed and presented, to serve as a platform for fuel sloshing investigations. The design procedure was shown and discussed, based on the classic aeroelastic scaling in two steps: scaling of the static behaviour of the model and matching of the scaled modal properties. An in-house genetic algorithm based optimization procedure was introduced and described, used for scaling where Nastran was used as an objective function generator. Scaling results with and without the fuel tank attached were presented and indicated the tank integration challenges. Experimental modal analysis was applied on the manufactured model without the tank attached and the data were used for the finite element model validation and updating. This work serves as a starting point in the understanding of the dynamics of the scaled wing structure in the "dry" (no liquid) configuration, which is essential for the planned liquid sloshing tests.

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